

ORION | Trapezium

A Monthly Publication of the ORION Astronomical Society

Total lunar eclipse image captured by Art Allison at TAO using his Seestar 50.
Timestamped 2:57 am Eastern 14 Mar 2025, just before greatest eclipse.

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Page Three Astronomy

How we did it.

This was taken at TAO, 4:05 am Eastern on 14 Mar 2025. Evidently our Moon is only about 16 cm in diameter. A detailed inspection reveals an on-off/color selector button underneath, and a tag that reads “Made in China.” Something for the flat Earthers, anti-science, and conspiracy theorists.

The **ORION Astronomical Society** is a science and astronomy group founded in April 1974 by scientists from the United States Department of Energy facilities at Oak Ridge, Tennessee. We primarily serve the communities of Oak Ridge and Knoxville and the counties of Anderson, Knox, and Roane.

ORION's mission is to support scientific research, teaching, and astronomical activities in East Tennessee. We hold monthly public meetings at the Oak Ridge RSCC Campus, and are active at Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO), hosting public events, sharing knowledge of the skies, and helping to provide intellectually stimulating programs. ORION works to share the wonders of the cosmos and the culture of science.

ORION members include scientists, engineers, technicians, IT experts, artists, students, and others with varied talents and expertise. Over half of ORION members own telescopes, many are amateur radio operators, and some have expertise in astrophotography.

ORION has working relationships with several organizations, including museums and other amateur astronomy groups. Membership is open to individuals who will actively contribute their time and ideas. The annual membership fee is \$20, and student discounts are available. There is no charge for our newsletters and publications, or for participation in most ORION activities.

ORION Board and Officers:

President: Don Spong

VP and Program Chair: David Fields

Social Chair: Noah Frere

Secretary: Rob Fowler

Treasurer: Bob Edwards

Editor: Ted Barnes

Astrotechnologist: Rob Scott

Videographer: Rob Fowler

Obed Site Outreach: Joshua Gray.

TRAPEZIUM is a monthly publication of the ORION Astronomical Society. The issue date is the Friday preceding the monthly ORION meeting, chosen to provide timely information regarding the planned Program.

From March 2025 we will be issuing a shorter version of the Trapezium, which will still include important information regarding the monthly ORION presentation, as well as dates and other information regarding Public Stargazes and other notable events relating to ORION and TAO.

We expect to go through several iterations of this shorter Trapezium; we have already decided that some components, such as a separate Astrophotography section, are so important for a publication on amateur astronomy that one really cannot justify excluding them.

Messages from ORION

During the last two weeks of March I was in Seville in Spain, attending and presenting a paper at the 18th Technical Meeting on Energetic Particles in Magnetic Confinement Systems. Due to the fact that several members of the program committee follow me on Facebook and knew that I did astrophotography, they asked me to also give a presentation on astrophotography at the end of the sessions on March 20, prior to the banquet. I put together a talk titled "Adventures in Astrophotography – Plasmas on a galactic scale," showing a collection of my solar, planetary, comet, galaxy and nebula images, making connections to fusion and plasma physics research where appropriate. It seemed to be quite successful, with many people expressing positive comments and asking me questions afterwards about how to get involved in the hobby. Astronomy seems to connect well with people, especially after sitting through 4 days of technical talks.

We are now moving into what is known as galaxy season, due the large number of galaxies that are in good positions for viewing and imaging. The Full Moon is on April 13th (also known as the Pink Moon) and the New Moon is on April 28th (a dark sky weekend is April 26-27). Planets visible in the evening during this period are Mars, Uranus, and Jupiter. The Lyrid Meteor Shower is at its peak April 21-22, although the Moon will be 40% illuminated. Deep space objects of interest for April include: M42 (Orion Nebula – the brightest in the sky); IC 434 (the Horsehead Nebula) in Orion; M106, 24 Mly away in the constellation Canis Venatici ("the hunting dogs"); M51 (the Whirlpool Galaxy), 31 Mly away, also in Canis Venatici; NGC 4449, an irregular galaxy 13 Mly away in Canis Venatici; M64 (the Black Eye Galaxy), 17 Mly away in Coma Berenices; M82 (the Cigar Galaxy), 12 Mly away in Ursa Major; and the Leo Triplet, which includes NGC 3628 (Sarah's Galaxy), M65, and M66. Double stars of interest in April include Mizar and Alcor in Ursa Major (the Big Dipper), and Cor Caroli, in Canes Venatici.

Observatory Way

The photo on the left shows our new road sign for the Roane State Tamke Allan Observatory. Traveling west, the sign is on the left as you turn into Observatory Way from Caney Creek Road, just past Joiner Hollow Road.

TAO Observatory Stargazes and Special Activities

TAO offers “dark sky” Stargazes to the community on the 1st and 3rd Saturdays of each month, weather permitting. The usual schedule for the winter is to open at 7 pm and continue nominally to 10 pm, but later if the sky and attendance encourage this. With DST we switch to 8 pm to 11 pm. These Stargazes are supported by local astronomy clubs, especially ORION members and friends, and benefit our students and community.

Our TAO Stargazes are usually well-attended, with a full classroom of visitors for evening astronomy lectures. We’ve recently missed some planned Stargazes due to inclement weather. Our next Public Stargaze is planned for the Saturday evening of April 19.

March 22 Asteroid Occultation / Telescope upgrades continuing

Our telescope upgrades include improving the image quality of our Meade LX200 telescope and continuing to develop remote telescope control capabilities. Here, Rob Fowler is adjusting the Meade (left), and at right we see Ted Barnes’ display showing an image of the March 22 occultation by asteroid 14 Irene.

TAO Director's Message (cont.)

Occultation of March 22

Our most recent attempt to capture an asteroid occultation of a star, at 11:00 pm Eastern on 22 Mar 2025, was very successful. Three simultaneous observations were made locally: Two at TAO, and another at Norris Lake State Park. Please see Ted's discussion in pp.31-46 of this issue of the Trapezium!

The image at right shows one of the TAO observations, by Ted Barnes using his 8" ORION RC Astrograph and gps-timed QHY174MGPS camera, viewed in real time on his SharpCap screen. The two points on the computer screen show a faint star and a fainter asteroid, approaching an eclipse of the star. In just a minute or two after I took this photo, the star disappeared from the display, and returned after 8.5 secs.

TAO Stargazes for International Friendship: April, 2025

TAO and ORION held our first International Friendship Stargaze at the International Friendship Bell on Monday evening, Feb. 3 and our second on March 6. This Bell is a historic venue for Oak Ridge we've had good participation from the RSCC Astronomy students and the public.

We started our April International Friendship Stargaze at 7:30 PM on April 8. Art Allison (left) and David were the first to arrive at the International Friendship Bell, and Art had already deployed his Seestar 50 telescope (on the far left). Each month, we meet at the International Friendship Bell choose an honored guest to strike the bell, beginning our stargaze. Art was the chosen Bell striker for our April 8 Stargaze. Art is a native-born citizen of the USA, but as a former commercial aircraft pilot, he has traveled internationally on many occasions.

TAO Director's Message (cont.)

Our April commemoration of International Friendship recalls the UN designation of this important concept. “Conscious of the need for the creation of conditions of stability and well-being and peaceful and friendly relations based on respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms for all without distinction as to race, sex, language or religion, the UN General Assembly declared 5 April the International Day of Conscience.” Thus our April event is an excellent opportunity for spring stargazing, renewal, and harmony.

As the evening progressed and skies darkened, other astronomers joined us and we had a good conversation and discussion of how early we prefer to meet in the future (just after sunset), where we will setup telescopes (probably on the grass, on the Southeast corner of the Bissell Park Senior Center Parking Lot), and planned program for TAO events and our April 16 ORION meeting. Here's a candid photo of some of the astronomers (others arriving later). I missed my chance to give a Vulcan wave.

TAO Director's Message (cont.)

Telescope optical and remote control developments; Asteroid occultation detection capability; and (in the context of) April 1-specific photo opportunity

We don't intentionally celebrate April 1, but we happened to be working at TAO, preparing for asteroid occultation coordination and attempting to take drone photos of the new site improvements. The opportunity arose to document one of our astronomers (Ted) with a telescope diffraction ring that he had fabricated (in the upper part of the image), and his new telescope LASER holder, shown in his left hand, throwing a LASER spot on the whiteboard behind. This moment clearly had to be recorded. Thanks to Ted Barnes and Rob Fowler for their work these last few months improving the performance of our Meade LX200 telescope and working out procedures for capturing images of asteroid occultations.

TAO Director's Message (cont.)

TAO Site Upgrades (1)

Finally we have our new sidewalks and viewing platforms.

TAO Director's Message (cont.)

TAO Site Upgrades (2)

The view to the South better illustrates the potential of our new pads..

ORION Monthly Meeting

ORION Monthly Meeting Format

Meeting Venue: City Room (A-111), just inside the main entrance, Coffey/McNalley Bldg., Oak Ridge Campus, Roane State Community College.

7:00 pm Eastern, 3rd Wednesday of each month.

Our monthly meetings (except for December, a dinner) generally proceed as follows:

- Welcome
- Announcements
- Invited Presentation and Discussion
- Awarding of the Mug
- Astrophotography / Special Presentations

The nominal start time is 7:00 pm Eastern, on the 3rd Wednesday of the month. The beginning of the meeting will usually include announcements of general interest.

Meetings typically continue until around 9:00 pm. Please plan to stay until the end. Hopefully we will all enjoy the astrophotography and other special topics discussed in the latter part of the meeting.

Remote Viewing: A live Zoom session will usually be open during the ORION Monthly Meeting, at the link:

<https://us02web.zoom.us/j/88528735960?pwd=KzY4bnBHcjlhTzg3L3pOcjY0TFovUT09> or
<https://bit.ly/42apGxX>

Meeting ID: 885 2873 5960 Passcode: 716689

Title: The Younger Dryas Cold Event

Speaker: Gareth Davies

Abstract:

A few decades ago a friend/colleague and I collected speleothem samples (calcite, travertine, stalagmites) from a cave in Wales to obtain Uranium-series dates of them. Uranium is soluble in bicarbonate waters but thorium (Th) and protactinium (Pa) (in the same geochemical conditions) are not. So uranium (mostly ^{238}U), which is present in trace amounts in natural waters is incorporated in cave deposits in calcite generally as a closed system. The ^{238}U decays via short-lived ^{234}Th and ^{234}Pa to longer lived ^{234}U . This decays to ^{230}Th and thus allows an age of the deposits to be determined with a dating range from, depending on the uranium concentration in the waters, about 1,000 years to $> 350,000$ years. We collected samples from geologically discernible locations so we could interpret the history of the deposition and erosion in that location in the cave passages. Uranium and thorium are chemically separated and purified from daughter isotopes and counted and analyzed by alpha spectrometry to calculate the age.

Title: The Younger Dryas Cold Event**Speaker: Gareth Davies****Abstract (cont.):**

One sample was a small stalagmite that was dated using a TIMS (Thermal Ionization Mass Spectrometer) which yields the most precise ages. The ages determined of this deposit showed it had grown between about 4 ka and 14 ka (ka = thousand years before the present). The Younger Dryas event occurred at about 12.9 ka. Recently a cosmic impact hypothesis of the cause of the YD has been put forward (Firestone *et al.*, 2006). No speleothem growth was recorded in stalagmite during the YD cold event. Glacial deposits outside of and near the cave relatively date to the same cold period. If the cause of the YD is explained by a cosmic impact then that it lasted ~1,000 years has an explanation too. That explanation might have an a similar developing scenario today, not of comic impact origin, but that might cause humankind significant problems.

Mini Bio:

From high-school in South Wales, UK, Gareth became interested in mountains and caves and was soon led into sampling cave water, doing lab chemistry, and tracing groundwaters with fluorescent dyes as part of a cave research project. After a serving the Royal Air Force and working as an air traffic controller in civilian aviation he moved to the US. He gained a B.S. (Geology) at Millsaps College in 1984, and an M.S. at the University of Southern Mississippi, in 1987, (Geology), finishing a karst-related thesis on uranium-series dating of speleothems from two caves in Tennessee. He has authored or co-authored more than 50 published papers. He has worked in a variety of geological settings from the tropical karst of Southeast Asia to the U.S. Rocky Mountains in crystalline rocks. He is a Fellow of the Geological Society of America.

Events and Calendars, Sky Map and Asteroids

Star, Moon, Comet and Meteorgazing at TAO in 2025

We enthusiastically invite visitors to attend our Public Stargaze events, held at our dark-sky site, the Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO) near Kingston, Tennessee. These events are intended especially for visitors, so our buildings and facilities will be open, and there will be astronomy talks as well as public skywatching.

In Jan-Jun 2025 we plan to hold fixed-calendar public Stargaze events on the 1st and 3rd Saturday of each month. These weekend events are especially appropriate for families. We also hold public special events, such as a “Full Moonrise,” with associated Moon Music, and the occasional comet watch. The annual Perseid Meteor watch in mid-August is especially popular.

The precise dates of many of these events depend on the local weather conditions, and cannot be specified *definitively* long in advance. As an approximate guide, see the TAOCalendar pages following. Once a date is finalized we usually confirm it through the ORION online message site ORION astronomy@groups.io. Likely and unlikely dates for TAO events may be inferred from the weather predictions at TAO by Clear Sky Charts (cleardarksky dot com) and Astrospheric (astrospheric dot com).

Please confirm event dates before proceeding to TAO.

In view of the rather challenging approach road to TAO, “Observatory Way,” first-time visitors should plan to arrive before dark. Driving instructions are given at: <https://www.roanestate.edu/pages/obs/visit.htm>

Some instructions follow, since people may be unfamiliar with procedures for stargazing at a dark-sky site.

ORION members are invited to arrive early with their telescopes and mounts, to prepare for evening observing and to share refreshments. Please bring a red flashlight, or a headband with a red-light option.

Visitors who wish to acquire red lights or red-light headbands for observing may find them at many commercial amateur astronomy sites, such as [https:// www dot high pointscientific dot com](https://www.highpointscientific.com). The “Lepro LE” LED Headlamp, model 3200008, available from Amazon for about \$10 (Aug. 2024) is a personal favorite. This is rechargeable and has separate red and white led buttons, with several brightness settings. A caution: For amateur astronomy, brighter lights are NOT preferred, and WHITE lights are highly discouraged. Please use only red lights while the Stargaze is in progress.

Parking is available on site; on entering TAO **stay to the right**, and *please use the parking area below and right (Southwest) of the TAO buildings and observing area, near the treeline*. And **PLEASE NO HEADLIGHTS ON SITE.**

Visitors are encouraged to interact with ORION astronomers who have set up and may be operating telescopes and other astronomical equipment. We enjoy public discussions, and regard this sharing of information as a primary goal of our organization. Visitors are welcome to coffee and other refreshments.

TAO Public Stargazing: A Note Regarding Scheduling and Access in 2025

In 2025 we will revert to an earlier schedule of having our Public Stargaze nights on every first and third Saturday. Of course this assumes good weather; if the weather is not suitable, a changed schedule will be announced on the group site [ORIONastronomy @ groups.io](https://www.groups.io/g/ORIONastronomy).

We decided that the previous (2024) schedule of a once-monthly Public Stargaze was insufficient, and having a Moon visible in some phase other than close to New gives our visitors an obvious and interesting object for viewing.

During Daylight Savings Time (mid-March through early November) we plan to hold our Public Stargaze events over the hours 8:00 pm - 11:00 pm. The planned Public Stargaze dates in Apr and Mar of 2025 are 5 Apr, 19 Apr, 3 May and 17 May.

If it is already dark when you arrive, please dim your headlights on the TAO grounds, follow the right branch of the access road, and park to the right of the TAO building, near the treeline.

Note: Parking in or near the elevated flat observing area at the front (East) of the TAO building is reserved for astronomers who are bringing their equipment.

Additional information for visitors may be found on the previous and following two pages of this issue.

TAO Public Stargazes in April:

Sat 05 & 19 Apr 2025

Sat 05 Apr 2025

Sunset	8:05 pm
Civ dusk	8:31 pm
Ast dusk	9:33 pm
Moonrise	1:05 pm
Moonset*	4:15 am
	*06 Apr
Moon illum.	54%

Gibbous Moon during this event.

Sat 19 Apr 2025

Sunset	8:17 pm
Civ dusk	8:43 pm
Ast dusk	9:49 pm
Moonrise	1:56 am
Moonset	11:16 am
Moon illum.	75%

No Moon during this event.

Since many TAO Public Stargazes in 2025 had already been cancelled due to cold weather or cloudy skies (5 of the first 6), we had hopes for 5 Apr, and during the week before this event the weather predictions appeared at least useable, if not especially good. Both CSC and Astrospheric predicted light clouds in the early evening, with an increase to about 50% overcast by midnight. One should be able to do *something* with a sky like that.

However on 5 Apr, while leaving the Oak Ridge area for TAO about 5 pm (accompanied by my step-daughter Beth Bredesen for her first TAO visit), we observed an essentially 100% pearly high overcast with small cumulus clouds beneath. This was perhaps slightly better at TAO, but only because one could see an occasional faintly blue region in the overcast sky.

Beth Bredesen greeting three guests from Knoxville, who found us by looking for “observatories” online.

David Fields had cancelled the 5 Apr Public Stargaze that morning when it became clear that the already mediocre weather forecast had deteriorated. The sky was basically overcast later that day, and appeared hopeless. So, since some of us had already planned trips to TAO, we made the best of it; David and I (Ted) gave presentations to our three visitors and the others present (Art Allison, Beth Bredesen, Rob Fowler, and Sunny the Astrodog), including what alas couldn't be seen in the sky tonight, and what we *had* recently done to record the asteroid occultation of 22 Mar 2025 involving 14 Irene.

I had hoped to image a newly announced near Earth asteroid, 2025 BC 10, but this was impossible given the overcast sky.

So, Rob and I proceeded to a gps timing experiment I hoped to use to test the accuracy or at least consistency of our two gps timing devices, one attached to the Meade LX200, and the other on the QHY174MGPS camera I use to time occultations with my Ritchey-Chrétien Astrograph. I adapted an Arduino microprocessor based LED flasher circuit I had assembled in early 2024 for use as a synthetic occultation signal, simply by inverting the operation to usually on, occasionally off. I set the program to a 10 second repeat cycle, with an off period of 100 ms. The idea is to records the same visual signal using both gps based recording systems, and compares their recorded times of disappearance and reappearance of that signal.

My initial concern was that the synthetic target star (LED) might be too faint, but on setting it up just West of the new large concrete pad at TAO, we found that it was actually quite bright; my impression was that it resembled a bright Venus in brilliance at that distance. Certainly the luminosity of this source needs to be reduced considerably if it is to represent for example a 10th magnitude star being occulted.

In any case Rob used it with the Meade and a ZWO ASI294MCP to generate images of this artificial occultation, with frame times of 50 ms down to 1 ms. The gain was set to very low values; these tests will certainly be repeated in future with a lower luminosity “stellar” source.

After a bout of low enthusiasm, brought on by realizing that I had even forgotten my headlamp, Rob and Beth assisted me in setting up the Ritchey-Chrétien on the dark, overcast TAO grounds. Once it was assembled (ignoring CPWI and the drive, since this was only to capture images of the Arduino light source), I started SharpCap and began looking for the LED signal. Nothing but a tiny raindrop. Raindrop? There was consensus that a light rain was just beginning. So, we decided that it really was time to quit, we could compare gps timings in future. We departed about 11 pm, having achieved little that night, but having a better idea about how to proceed with gps tests.

Art and David consider how to handle alleged UFO sightings.
TAO lecture room, 9:40 pm Eastern, 5 Apr 2025.

A new series of monthly Stargaze events was initiated in Oak Ridge on Monday 03 Feb 2025, with the April event planned for Tue 08 Apr 2025. ORION plans to continue these monthly International Friendship Stargaze (IFS) events near the Peace Bell in A. K. Bissell Park.

This event is intended to bring enjoyment of the evening skies to people in the Oak Ridge, Clinton and surrounding areas who may find the 30-mile trip to TAO for one of our existing bimonthly 1st and 3rd Sat Public Stargaze events too onerous. Although the background light levels are rather high in the Oak Ridge area, it is still possible to view interesting objects such as the Moon, planets and stars through our telescopes.

Dates for future IFS Stargazes will be announced in the Trapezium, and on the ORIONastronomy at groups.io.

If the weather predictions for this date prove to be unfavorable, a change of plans will be announced on ORION astronomy at groups.io. It may be useful to follow the Oak Ridge area astronomy weather predictions on Clear Sky Charts (cleardark sky dot com) and Astrospheric (astrospheric dot com), to see whether the weather (smile emoji) for the planned date appears favorable in advance.

Visitors are encouraged to interact with ORION astronomers who have set up and may be operating telescopes and other astronomical equipment. We enjoy public discussions, and regard this sharing of

information as a primary goal of our organization.

Please confirm the time and date of the event in advance before proceeding to the site, as these may have been changed.

Parking is available nearby, near the Oak Ridge Social Center building in the park; it's a short walk from there to the Peace Bell area. Since this is not a dark-sky location, no special lighting preparations are required, although those who have astronomy headlights may wish to bring them. Similarly, people who wish to bring their own outdoor seating, binoculars, telescopes and so forth are welcome to participate.

During DST (Apr-Oct IFS events), public telescope viewing in future will normally be from 8:00 pm until 9:00 pm, longer if there is public interest. Outside of DST, all these times will be an hour earlier. The early times of this event are chosen with school age kiddies in mind.

1st IFS Stargaze, Mon 03 Feb 2025.

The April IFS Stargaze underwent several last minute changes of date and time before finally being reset to 7:30 pm Eastern, 08 Apr 2025. The originally listed time had been 8:00 pm on Tue 08 Apr, but this was changed to 7:30 pm on Thu 10 Apr 2025. However the weather predicted for Thu was rainy, so the date was moved back to Tue 08 Apr, predicted to be clear but cold. The time was left at 7:30 pm, although this was well before sunset. David Fields has been preparing an announcement for the nearby Oak Ridge Library, since announcing it in ORION Astronomy alone had little effect, but this item was not yet available. The initial IFS event had a recommended time for equipment setup, but that has now been removed. Clearly better publicity is needed, since the March event had few attendees. Having Noah's Astronomy students there in Feb and Mar had been most helpful!

So, several ORION members duly arrived before 7:30 pm for the Apr event. Rob Fowler and I (Ted Barnes) arrived at the elevated parking area and set up our camping chairs at the edge where we had a good view to the West. The sun was still far above the horizon (sunset was close to 8:00 pm, probably a better time for the event). A few joggers and a family or two were visible, but the park was almost deserted. It was quite cold. I had set up my remote telescope in Clinton and had a table and cpu with me to view it, but we had no public attendees so I left the equipment in my van.

Eventually we heard a few gongs of the Peace Bell,, and through the trees I could

see David Fields and Art Allison. Rob and David discussed the situation by cell phone, and David and Art came up and joined us at our elevated viewing site. Sitting in a camping chair looking down on the park as the sun set and stars began to appear was not unpleasant. As the time passed we were joined by Robert Varner and Juan Carbajo, so we had an audience of six ORION people and no visitors, watching the stars appear, adding to a bright Moon high in the Southeast. Several people fortunately had binoculars. We started with Jupiter and Sirius, and as it darkened we added Procyon, Capella, Betelgeuse, Rigel, Aldebaran, Bellatrix, Saiph, and Orion's Belt. We departed about 9:00 pm. As we departed I passed two other astronomers who missed us, and thought we had cancelled. That's 8.

In discussing the event we agreed that it had started too early, and that in future months, as the weather warms, we may attract visitors already in the park for a stroll in the evening, who happen to walk past where we are setting up.

3rd IFS Stargaze, 25
8:08 pm Eastern, Tue 08 Apr 2025.

TAO Calendars

Jan-Jun 2025; Apr & May 2025

The principle public events for visitors at TAO are the **Public Stargazes**, held at TAO during 2025 on the 1st and 3rd Saturday of each month. These are listed in the “**Public Fixed Events**” **TAO Calendar** for a six month period, currently Jan-Jun 2025. This appears on the page following.

Additional notable events will be included in monthly “**Special Events**” **TAO Calendars**. These include public events that do not have a fixed date long in advance, such as the **International Friendship Stargaze** in Oak Ridge, and special TAO events such as **Asteroid Occultations, Meteor Showers, Full Moonrises, Lunar (and other) Eclipses, Comet Watches**, and perhaps the occasional musical event.

These “Special Events” calendars for the current and subsequent months appear after the six-month “Public Fixed Events” calendar.

The facilities in the TAO buildings onsite will be open to the public during the “Public Fixed Events,” and will also usually be available when TAO is open to the public for some of the “Special Events.” **Please inquire regarding whether TAO will be open to the public for any “Special Event” you may wish to attend, since some may be restricted.** We will of course always try to accommodate enthusiastic visitors.

We recommend checking a TAO website such as **ORIONAstronomy @ groups.io** before visiting, to confirm that listed events will proceed as planned; weather conditions for example may require a cancellation or change of date.

TAO Calendar Public Fixed Events

Jan-Jun 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Sat 04 Jan 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 18 Jan 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 01 Feb 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 15 Feb 2025	<small>cancAlled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 01 Mar 2025	<small>cancAlled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 15 Mar 2025	<small>cancAlled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 05 Apr 2025	<small>cancAlled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 19 Apr 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 03 May 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	9:00 pm	midnight
Sat 17 May 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	9:00 pm	midnight
Sat 07 Jun 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	9:00 pm	midnight
Sat 21 Jun 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	9:00 pm	midnight

These first-half of 2025 TAO Public Events are scheduled for fixed calendar days during the weekend, which will hopefully prove convenient for many visitors with families, especially those bringing younger astronomers. Cancellations often take place in Winter, due to cold or icy conditions or overcast skies.

TAOCalendar Special Events

Apr 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Sat 05 Apr 2025	<small>cancelled</small> 	1 st Sat Public Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Tue 08 Apr 2025		International Friendship Stargaze (Oak Ridge)	7:30 pm	9:00 pm
Sat 12 Apr 2025		Full Moon 08:22 pm Eastern		
Mon 14 Apr 2025		Asteroid Occultation 785 Zwetana 01:46:20 am Eastern	5:30 pm	3:00 am
Sat 19 Apr 2025		3 rd Sat Public Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sun 27 Apr 2025		New Moon 03:31 pm Eastern		

TAOCalendar Special Events

May 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Sat 03 May 2025		1 st Sat Public Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
t.b.a. May 2025		International Friendship Stargaze (Oak Ridge)	8:00 pm	9:00 pm
Mon 12 May 2025		Full Moon 02:56 pm Eastern		
Sat 17 May 2025		3 rd Sat Public Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Mon 26 May 2025		New Moon 11:02 pm Eastern		

The evening Sky Map, Apr 2025, from skymaps.com .

Note: a nice interactive sky chart from Sky and Telescope may be found at this link...
<https://skyandtelescope.org/interactive-sky-chart/>

Occultation by Asteroid 14 Irene at TAO on 22 Mar 2025.

- Ted Barnes

One learns about asteroid occultations that will be visible from a specified location from the output of the program Occult Watcher, which is available as a download from the International Occultation Timing Association IOTA, at <https://www.occultwatcher.net>.

Although occultations are reported by Occult Watcher rather frequently, typically with a new one every few days, they tend to occur at unsociable times such as 4 am, or involve faintish stars such as 13th magnitude or dimmer. And the asteroid is often even fainter, whereas one might occasionally like to observe both the asteroid AND the occulted “target” star. The duration of a typical occultation is a half second to a few seconds; it is unusual to find one as long as ten seconds. Other complications include having a bright Moon, or being near sunrise or sunset. And inclement weather typically removes perhaps 2/3 of potential occultations from visibility.

Occasionally a special occultation appears in the list, in which the star is “bright” (in this business that means brighter than magnitude 10.0), and the event is of long duration, because it involves a large asteroid (an early discovery, with a low asteroid number).

Recently a truly notable occultation appeared in the list of coming events visible at TAO, the occultation of a “bright” (magnitude 9.5) star by a large asteroid, 14 Irene, with a diameter of about 150 km. This would take place in Gemini, at Alt@Azi = 56° @ 271° (high but not terribly so, and to the West, a dark direction at TAO). The predicted time was a very civilized 11:00:33 pm Eastern, Sat 22 Mar 2025. There would be no Moon visible (Alt -56°), and the predicted maximum duration was a very long 11.2 seconds! Everything about this event sounded attractive, it was the best in months. The only concern was the weather, but at 10 days out the weather appeared favorable, and as the date approached the predicted weather remained excellent.

The location of 14 Irene in the solar system at the time of the occultation is shown on the following page, in an orbit diagram from JPL Horizons. Evidently, as seen from Earth, Mars and 14 Irene would be in similar locations, and indeed both were in Gemini during the event.

Occultation by Asteroid 14 Irene (cont.)

JPL/Horizons diagram showing the inner solar system and the position of 14 Irene at the time of the occultation.

Occultation by Asteroid 14 Irene (cont.)

A sky chart generated using TheSkyX showing the location of the occultation, near the Gemini-Auriga border.

The location of 14 Irene and the target star TYC 1892-00151-1 at the time of the occultation. The nearest “bright” star is 7th magnitude HIP32014; it and the 9.5 magnitude target star itself are shown in a finer-scale chart on the page following.

Occultation by Asteroid 14 Irene (cont.)

A sky chart at the predicted time of the occultation, generated using TheSkyX. This shows the full field of view (1920x1200 pixels, purple rectangle) anticipated for the 8" Orion Ritchey-Chrétien Astrograph attached to the QHY174MGPS camera, both used during this event. 14 Irene appears reassuringly superimposed on the target star TYC 1892-00151-1, at the J2000.0 coordinates RA 06 40 56.4, Dec +29 45 23. (The coordinate grid labels use apparent equinox coordinates, not J2000.0.) Predictions for the event time varied from 11:00:32 to 11:00:34 pm Eastern, depending on the source consulted. This chart shows stars to approximate magnitude 14.0. HIP 32014 and the three base stars below it form the neoasterism "Fowler's Chair."

Occultation by Asteroid 14 Irene (cont.)

This Occult Watcher image shows the predicted local trajectory of the shadow of 14 Irene on the Earth's surface. For typical asteroids the shadow might be 5 or 10 km in diameter; in this case it is about 150 km in diameter, and covers a large fraction of East Tennessee. The telescope icon indicates the location of TAO. The shadow centerline is green, the shadow edge is blue, and the white line is a chord along the shadow's direction of travel that intersects TAO. Since TAO is about 61 km from the centerline and the edge is 75 km from centerline, one would expect the maximum duration to be reduced by about a factor of $\sqrt{1-(61/75)^2} = 0.58$, assuming a spherical asteroid. This would reduce the predicted maximum duration of 11.2 secs on the centerline to 6.5 secs at TAO's location.

Occultation by Asteroid 14 Irene (cont.)

Since occultation observations are intricate procedures that often involve unexpected technical problems with equipment, past experience suggested that we should have a trial run before the actual event. This is early in setup of that trial run on 21 Mar 2025 at TAO, the night before the actual occultation. One can see my workbench with my cpu and two monitors, and behind that the 8" Ritchey-Chrétien Astrograph I have used recently for occultations. One problem was a nearly overcast sky, which took several hours to clear. Afterwards, I found difficulties in capturing frames of 20 ms length which I had hoped to use, and had to lengthen them to 50 ms for this event. Rob Fowler also had problems with operating the Meade LX200, which was dropping its wifi comm link to his cpu.

Occultation by Asteroid 14 Irene (cont.)

7:08 pm Eastern, a remarkably clear blue sky at TAO on the evening of the occultation.

10:32 pm Eastern. Rob attempting to hold the Meade onto the position of the coming occultation, in Gemini. This is just over 28 minutes before the event.

The date of the occultation, Sat 22 Mar 2025, proved to be a strikingly beautiful day. Rob and I arrived about 7 pm and began setting up, accompanied by David Fields. Not long after we were joined by Bob Edwards and Jim Lord; this was Jim's first occultation.

Occultation by Asteroid 14 Irene (cont.)

Bob Edwards, Jim Lord and David Fields (L to R), inside the TAO building at 10:32 pm Eastern as the time of the occultation approaches. Our emergency rations included freshly baked bread, hummus and pita chips, and (c/o Jim) a large pineapple upside-down cake.

Occultation by Asteroid 14 Irene (cont.)

A near full-field (1600x1200) image of the target star (L) and asteroid (R) as a close double near the center of the image, at 11:46:29 pm Eastern, 14 minutes before the occultation. This is a 4 sec single exposure at maximum gain, hence 4sG480. This image was rotated by 180° to give the standard orientation of N up and E left, so the asteroid is approaching from the right. (Note the gps timestamp is inverted.) Another last minute technical snag was a persistent amp glow (visible at left), which fortunately didn't affect the fast, small-field 50 ms frames.

Occultation by Asteroid 14 Irene (cont.)

Starting at 11:00:23.5798131 pm Eastern I captured 400 short frames of size 320x240 px. Exposure, processing and storage used approx 59 ms for each frame. The transition to dim (star eclipse starting, top row, red frames) involved frames 91-92-93, and the transition to bright (star eclipse ending, bottom row, blue frames) involved frames 234-235-236. These gave estimated start and end times of 11:00:28.98 pm and 11:00:37.43 pm Eastern, with estimated errors of +/- 0.03 sec. These imply an event midpoint at TAO of 11:00:33.21(2) pm Eastern and a duration of 8.45(4) secs. These values were reported to IOTA on 25 Mar 2025.

Ocultation by Asteroid 14 Irene (cont.)

This is a final (live) image of the outside display from my cpu about 17 minutes after the event; 14 Irene is departing to the right. (This image has N down and E right.) One of the surprises from this event was how quickly the asteroid was seen to separate from the star in these small-scale 320x240 px images. Given the drift velocity of 14 Irene (mainly in RA), and the pixel size of 0.748 asecs, one could show that the asteroid moved at about 0.82 px/min. Thus 10 minutes was sufficient to easily separate the images of star and asteroid before and after the event. During the event itself, on this screen we could easily see the asteroid and star drop to a much fainter combined magnitude. A first for our group! After the event ended we celebrated with several enthusiastic choruses of “Goodnight, Irene!”

My final report to IOTA appears on the following page.

Occultation by Asteroid 14 Irene (cont.)

Observation was:

Positive

Asteroid Occultation Report Form

All times MUST be reported using UTC

V5.6.11

Mailing Address: 182 Burley Nelson Lane

Phone: 2404839608

City, State, Country: Clinton, Tennessee, USA

Fax:

Observing Location:

Rockwood, Tennessee, USA

<--(nearest City/Town, with State/Country only)

Location:

Latitude: deg mm sec.ss N/S 35 49 56.70 N Longitude: deg mm sec.ss E/W 84 37 04.30 W Elevation: 324 m Datum: Other

Telescope:

Aperture: 20.0 cm f/ratio: 8.0 Magnification: Type: Newtonian

Timing:

GPS - other linking

Method: Video with frame analysis

Asteroid visible before/during occ? yes

Timing Device:

Other - Specify in Comments

OTE Used: Other - Specify in Comments

Detector:

Model/Type: Other - List in Comments

Video Format: FITS Images

Exposure Integration: #N/A

Unit Fields

Other Detector related info

50ms frames, gain 480, ROI 320x240.

Enter Times in Manually-Corrected Fields

Conditions:

Clouds: Clear

Stability: Steady

Other conditions: no moon, sky excellent

Observations:

#N/A

	Times	Accuracy	PE	Remark
	hh mm ss.sss	Level Error Bars In Boxes Below		
Started Observing:	03 00 23.58	0.03		Captured 400 50ms frames (avg duration 59ms due to overheads). Transitional frames were 92 and 235. Used bin midpoint for time, estm error +/- 0.03 sec = +/- half of bin width. Results are local occultation midpt 03:00:33.21(2) UT and duration 8.45(4) secs.
Manually-Corrected Disappearance:	03 00 28.980	0.03		
Manually-Corrected Reappearance:	03 00 37.430	0.03		Assuming a max dur on midline of 11.2 sec, our location 61.06 km fm center, and a shadow edge at 75.79 km, assuming a spherical asteroid we would expect a 6.6 sec duration. Thus our observed duration 8.45 +/- 0.04 secs is about 30% longer than naively expected.
Stopped Observing:	03 00 47.2	0.03		
	hh mm ss.sss	68.3%; 95.0%; 99.7%	< 95% confidence level will be reported to IOTA	no Was this a Miss?

no 2nd star visible? Select Yes if this report is for the second star of a double.

S/N = (if known)

Additional

Successful obs of occultation with timing. 100% clear skies. Full report will follow. Telescope model 8267 8-in Orion RC astrograph. Detector QHY174MGPS camera. We concurrently observed this occultation with a 12-in Celestron LX-200, operated by Rob Fowler, also at TAO. The start and stop observing (= recording) times above are for frames 1 and 400, start and end thereof. Report prepopulated by IOTA Reporting Add-in for OW ver. 1.9. Jpgs not FITS.

Comments

Email report to: reports@asteroidoccultation.com

If available please include a Tangra or Limovie CSV file of the light curve data with the report.

The final report on the occultation, submitted to IOTA on 25 Mar 2025.

Occultation by Asteroid 14 Irene (cont.)

DARK STAR AWARD

*Occultation of star TYC 1892-00151-1 by 14 Irene
at TAO, 11:00:33 pm Eastern 22 Mar 2025*

Awardee: J. Lord

Occultation by Asteroid 14 Irene (cont.)

One might have thought that the end of the story of the successful observation of the occultation by 14 Irene on 22 Mar 2025. However it wasn't.

The next day, Sunday 23 Mar 2025, I received an email from Richard Piety regarding the occultation, in which he says

“Thought you might be interested in the data I got on the occultation last night at Norris State Park. You can download it at [url] if you are interested. Each frame has a UTC timestamp.

The star in the center is TYC 1892-00151-1 and in the last 40 frames it clearly dims for about 22 frames. The file is about 500 MBytes. I couldn't manage to shorten the file without losing data.

*Regards,
Richard Piety”*

Well that was a surprise! Richard had extracted the necessary information from a talk I had given (at the monthly ORION meeting), and had successfully captured the occultation while observing at Norris State Park! I only found his email on 25 Mar.

After a few email iterations I learned that he had captured 0.5 sec frames, but didn't have a gps timing reference, so his time stamps were based on his computer's clock. This meant that his “absolute” times were incorrect by an unknown common systematic error. However intervals should still be reasonably accurate. Subtracting the times of his first and last dimmed bins, one finds an eclipse duration of 13.0 secs, rather larger than the predicted maximum duration of 11.2 secs.

For an error estimate, using start and stop time errors of ± 0.25 secs (\pm half a bin width), the difference time should have an approximate error of $\sqrt{2} * 0.25$ secs = 0.35 secs, hence the observed duration to 1 place accuracy is 13.0(4) secs.

This is much larger than our observed duration at TAO of 8.45(4) secs, largely because TAO was not far from the edge of the asteroid. The ratio of durations is 0.65(2), whereas from TAO's position and assuming a spherical asteroid, one would expect a duration ratio of 0.58. Fairly good agreement!

Occultation by Asteroid 14 Irene (cont.)

As regards the midpoint time, as noted above this will be skewed by the unknown cpu clock systematic error. However we can proceed, keeping this in mind. The middle of the first and last dimmed frames reported by Richard (in UT 03:00:ss.ss format) are 28.51(25) sec and 41.03(25) sec, so the mean of these times is 34.77(18) secs. Rounding gives an estimated midpt time at NLO of UT 03:00:34.8(2) secs.

In comparison at TAO I had an estimated midpt time of UT 03:00:33.21(2) secs. Thus the TAO midpt (with gps sync) leads the estimated midpoint at NLO by 1.6(2) secs.

But is this an actual discrepancy? The NLO site is about 23 km downpath from the TAO site, so one expects the TAO midpt time to lead the NLO midpt time by an estimated 1.7 secs.

This is remarkably good agreement between the TAO midpt time and the NLO midpt time, with a delay due to the longer asteroid path to NLO. Of course the agreement implicitly assumes that Richard's cpu clock at NLO and my (Ted's) gps clock at TAO we in agreement to an accuracy of *ca.* 0.2 secs. We are fortunate if this was the case. Anyway, we can see that a 1.7 sec discrepancy was expected!

The longer than expected durations seen by both NLO and TAO may indicate a departure from sphericity on the part of 14 Irene, or she may just have been a bit larger than stated in the JPL Horizons database.

In any case the NLO observation certainly merits an award!

Occultation by Asteroid 14 Irene (cont.)

DARK STAR AWARD

*Occultation of star TYC 1892-00151-1 by 14 Irene
at NLO, 11:00:33 pm Eastern 22 Mar 2025*

Awardee: R. Piety

Surprise Dark Stargaze of

Tue 01 Apr 2025

Occasionally we have a nearly spontaneous Dark Stargaze event at TAO mainly for the ORION Staff, for example when a clear sky is predicted, and the day has been a beautiful eggshell blue, often the day after a heavy rainstorm. Since we have our weekly ORION Board Meeting on Mondays at the ElCantarito restaurant in Oak Ridge, a clear sky can motivate a trip to TAO that night or perhaps the following night, depending on local events and the predicted weather.

Tue 01 Apr 2025

Sunset	8:02 pm
Civ dusk	8:27 pm
Ast dusk	9:29 pm
Moonrise	9:13 am
Moonset*	12:25 am
	* 2 Apr

Moon illum. 13%

This was one such event. At the Monday lunch we agreed that Tuesday, April Fool's Day, had a nice sky predicted, so that would be a Dark Stargaze, with arrival at the TAO gate planned for 7:00 pm.

Crescent Moon during this event.

ORION President Don Spong setting up in the unaccustomed luxury of the new 20 ft sq concrete pad at TAO, 7:42 pm Eastern, 1 Apr 2025. This is the new pad's first astronomical activity. Note misleading blue sky.

Surprise Dark Stargaze (cont.)

Three of us, Art, Rob and Ted, were early enthusiastic arrivals at TAO gate on Tues 01 April 2025, and were all there by 6:40 pm. David arrived about 7:15 pm, and Don soon afterwards, so we had a group of 5 senior astronomers plus Sunny the Astrodog.

Perhaps not surprisingly for April Fool's Day, the weather quickly deteriorated from a mostly clear sky to a misty low haze with few stars visible. It did clear afterwards, first in regions (see below), then by 11 pm to a surprisingly clear sky almost everywhere. But by then we were discouraged, and all departed soon before midnight.

Rob aligning the Meade LX200 on Sirius from within the glowdome, 9:54 pm. Left and below Canis Major one can see deep Southern stars in Puppis, including the famous O5Ia supergiant Naos (ζ Pup) at -40.0° Dec, just above the center of the dome. Up and left from Naos one can even see two stars in the underappreciated constellation Pyxis.

Surprise Dark Stargaze (cont.)

I had brought some art supplies to the event, and chopped an annular filter out of stiff black cardboard for the Meade LX200, hoping to block the optical anomaly that is visible as a bite in the Airy disk. (Filter radius dimensions 4.5" I.D., 6.5" O.D.) Perhaps surprisingly this filter fit nicely in the front of the OTA, see image below. Airy disks showed that it did succeed in blocking the optical anomaly. Images of "before" and "after" Airy disks of Betelgeuse are shown on the page following. Although the filter was successful, and it did removed scattered light from star images, the reduced aperture lost just over a magnitude in image brightness. We still hope to identify and correct the actual optical problem in the front of the OTA, whatever it is.

Surprise Dark Stargaze (cont.)

Airy disks of Betelgeuse, taken without (above) and with (below) the optical filter in place. Clearly the optical defect has been blocked, but at the cost of a factor of about 2.5 in light gathering power. Corresponding enlarged star images at focus without and with the filter in place (above and below respectively) are shown at right. One could increase the filter I.D. to 5.0" and recover some of the reduced aperture without losing the improved Airy disk and tighter star image. Perhaps next time?

Asteroid Flash ...

Next notable asteroid occultation at TAO:

Mon 14 Apr 2025, 01:46:20 am Eastern

Magnitude **11.1** star **TYC 2442-00543-1**
will be occulted in a repeat performance
by our old friend
the 50 km diameter, magnitude 14.3 asteroid

785 Zwetana

Max duration **2.4 seconds**

In Gemini, Alt @ Azi = 14° @ 301°

TAO 19 km from center line

Moon Alt @ Azi = 36° @ 167°

Moon distance 114°

Moon illumination 100%

Shop Talk

Meade LX200 Adventures and the Lunar Eclipse of 14 Mar.

- Ted Barnes

This story is a little complicated as it covers two topics on two disjoint days, developments regarding repair and refurbishment of the Meade LX200, on both 11 and 14 Mar 2025, *and* the observation and recording of the Total Lunar Eclipse at TAO on 14 Mar 2025. So, let's start at the beginning, with our initial pre-eclipse trip to TAO on Tue 11 Mar 2025.

i) 11 Mar 2025

David, Rob and I decided that there was sufficient motivation for a special trip to TAO on that date. First, I wanted to measure the Morrow-scope, since we had discussed looking for a dome for this telescope repeatedly, but no one had quite gotten around to measuring the scope when fully assembled. So we did that. The results are a separation between tripod leg end points (at bottom) of 35 in; a vertical distance from the floor to the platform the mount rests on of 38 in; the height of the scope from the floor to the highest point on the OTA, maybe a few inches less than 95 in (call it 8 ft to be cautious); the (intermediate) height of the scope from the floor to the top of the mounting plate for the OTA, 68 in.

Personally I might recommend that a dome provide at least 2 ft of clearance above the top of the OTA. Thus the dome interior ceiling level should be at least 10 ft. Rob and David agreed this was higher than they had expected.

Next we proceeded to work on the LX200 OTA. The names used may be a little confusing, since this Meade LX200 telescope sits atop a Celestron mount, of the venerable model CGE. Initially for fun I used AnyDesk to contact my home office computer at 9:07 pm, and instructed it to play some music for Agatha's benefit. This probably worked, and if so it was a record distance AnyDesk session for us of about 40 km, but Agatha was apparently asleep, and missed hearing the music. In the interim Rob set up his PC connection to the CGE through a wifi dongle, and aligned the LX200 using Caph, Alioth, Sirius and Rigel, using one of my ZWO ASI294MCP cameras. No one had brought binoculars (oops), so the alignment by eyeball of laser beam and stars was probably less accurate than one might have expected. I confirmed that a long USB3.0 cable I had purchased some time ago but never unwrapped (10 ft length I think) worked well for this exercise. I also used AnyDesk to connect my PC to Rob's, so some of the subsequent effort used both pcs.

We had hoped to use the Plate Solver on SharpCap to orient the Meade's camera to North by plate solving a star field, since SC displays a current camera angle with respect to N after plate solving. Alas Rob's two versions of SharpCap didn't have this recent Plate Solver function, so he had to resubscribe to SharpCap Pro and dnload the latest version. Although this dnload worked, we were still unable to successfully solve Meade star fields. SharpCap seemed to want more stars to solve the field than the ~ 20 to 56 it identified.

Meade LX200 Adventures and the Lunar Eclipse.

(cont.)

Here are two nice images of Rob (inside the dome) aligning the LX200 OTA on two bright stars to the South in Canis Major and Orion, using the scope control program CPWI and the LX200's newish laser pointer. The stars are of course Sirius (L) and Rigel (R) .

Meade LX200 Adventures and the Lunar Eclipse. (cont.)

Rob DID confirm on 11 Mar that the previous repair of the Meade LX200 focus knob on 03 Mar 2025 had not corrected the Airy disk problem. Two Airy disks that he captured on 11 Mar are shown below. The one at left looks very similar to our previous LX200 Airy disk images, and the one at right looks like the “cusp” disk we saw through an eyepiece after the LX200 repair effort of 03 Mar. This image at right is presumably the “left” Airy disk when viewed on the other side of the focal plane.

This speculation needs to be confirmed, as the two images were captured quickly late in the evening. The one at left, very similar in appearance to our earlier Airy disks, confirmed our suspicion that the optical flaw that produced the strange Airy disk had not been affected by the LX200 repair effort.

So, we departed TAO at about 11:30 pm, having confirmed to our satisfaction that the Airy disk problem remained unsolved..

Meade LX200 Adventures and the Lunar Eclipse. (cont.)

Now we proceed to 14 Mar 2025, including the observation of the Total Lunar Eclipse at TAO *and* further adventures with the LX200 on the same date. Let's start with our plans for viewing the Total Lunar Eclipse on 14 Mar 2025.

ii) 13-14 Mar 2025

Our chatter on WhatsApp regarding what we should do for the total lunar eclipse, the only one of 2025, only started seriously when it was already Thursday 13 Mar, the day immediately before eclipse night. People seemed to have conflicts (Noah and Rob), or just some kind of burnout from several recent and coming events. I said that I thought we really had to show up at TAO for an important event like this, and attempt some astrophotography. We could use the Meade, so equipment transport was not a problem. I suggested meeting around sunset. Art just wanted to know when to turn up. Apparently Juan said that he could just step outside to see the eclipse, so he saw no need to travel to TAO. David said that he had had a very long day and needed to rest before this very late event. According to the summary I found at Nasa's GSFC site <https://eclipse.gsfc.nasa.gov/eclipse.html>, although Penumbral contact started at 11:57 pm Eastern on 13 Mar, the deepest (Umbral) part of the eclipse lasted from 2:26 - 3:31 am Eastern, 14 Mar. Thus treating the eclipse with proper respect would require staying until at least 4 am. (In the event I actually left TAO at 4:38 am, 14 Mar 2025, so to my mind the Moon was adequately celebrated.)

David suggested that we arrive at TAO about 11 pm, which I thought was fine for this event. Art was still “Go.” I arrived at the gate of deep dark TAO about 10:45 pm, and Art was already there. David arrived soon after, and we began setting up. Here we see David and Art in the TAO classroom, waiting for the eclipse to intensify. Image time 1:29 am Eastern, about an hour before totality. David and Art had both brought Moon-related edibles.

Total Lunar Eclipse of 2025 Mar 14

Ecliptic Conjunction = 06:55:48.0 TD (= 06:54:33.5 UT)

Greatest Eclipse = 06:59:56.2 TD (= 06:58:41.7 UT)

Penumbral Magnitude = 2.2595 P. Radius = 1.1899° Gamma = 0.3484
 Umbral Magnitude = 1.1784 U. Radius = 0.6537° Axis = 0.3171°

Saros Series = 123 Member = 53 of 73

Sun at Greatest Eclipse
(Geocentric Coordinates)

R.A. = 23h37m46.0s
 Dec. = -02°24'16.8"
 S.D. = 00°16'05.2"
 H.P. = 00°00'08.8"

Moon at Greatest Eclipse
(Geocentric Coordinates)

R.A. = 11h38m23.0s
 Dec. = +02°40'54.6"
 S.D. = 00°14'52.8"
 H.P. = 00°54'36.8"

Eclipse Durations

Penumbral = 06h02m37s
 Umbral = 03h38m15s
 Total = 01h05m24s

ΔT = 75 s

Rule = CdT (Danjon)

Eph. = VSOP87/ELP2000-85

Eclipse Contacts

P1 = 03:57:24 UT
 U1 = 05:09:33 UT
 U2 = 06:25:59 UT
 U3 = 07:31:23 UT
 U4 = 08:47:48 UT
 P4 = 10:00:01 UT

F. Espenak, NASA's GSFC
eclipse.gsfc.nasa.gov/eclipse.html

A detailed chart of UT times of various aspects of the 14 Mar 2025 Total Lunar Eclipse. This is c/o NASA, as cited. Eastern times are UT - 4 hrs.

Meade LX200 Adventures and the Lunar Eclipse. (cont.)

Initially David wanted to stare into the Meade, to see if he could identify the defect responsible for the flawed Airy disk. (We had noticed earlier that the Airy disk problem had not been solved by Drew's earlier successful repair of the focus knob; the Airy disk only looked different on the 2 sides of the focal plane, corresponding to different focuser settings. One side still had the familiar dark edge "bite" that we had first observed months before; see the preceding notes in this article for 11 Mar 2025.) David wanted to try to clarify the location of the flaw, specifically its " ϕ " angle around the OTA. By holding up a yardstick while David watched the Airy disk through an eyepiece, we were able to identify the location as being just below the text "Meade LX200 EMC" on the exterior of the OTA, near a small white hand-drawn x just below the forward end of the OTA. There is a small dark grey annular gasket that sits just inside the front corrector plate on the Meade, and when it was opened inside the TAO classroom on 3 Mar 2025, it was evident that a short section was missing from this gasket. David suggested that this gasket anomaly might be the cause of the irregular Airy disk, as it appeared to be at about the same angle ϕ on the OTA. A very compelling suggestion! This can be easily tested by placing a small piece of black material of the same shape as the missing gasket section on the front of the OTA; does this repair the Airy disk? An important future next step in this long saga. It would also be interesting to prepare several OTA cutout masks of black construction paper to test their results on the Airy disk.

This shows the OTA with the glass corrector plate removed, in the TAO classroom on 3 Mar 2025. The gap in the annular gasket, which may be the origin of the irregularity in the Airy disk noted previously, is indicated by the red arrow.

Location of the gap in the annular gasket.

Meade LX200 Adventures and the Lunar Eclipse. (cont.)

This was very important, but we were after all present at TAO because of the lunar eclipse, and I was interested in getting the Meade to point at the Moon in the very near future. We had actually started the “bootup” procedure with the Meade earlier, at 10:20 pm Eastern, for this reason. I had brought two Celestron wifi dongles for the mount, and David used the first, in the aux1 socket. My PC “Sapphire,” a Win10 box, showed both the Celestron-C1F and observatory wifi signals, which connected to my pc’s wifi and wifi2 networks respectively.

I initially started CPWI with the wrong coordinates (Clinton, LRO, instead of TAO), so in the CPWI Alignment function I fixed this, and used Load Alignment to load a 10-star TAO pointing model from 28 Jan 2025 (the only one I had that was marked TAO; there were about a dozen from LRO).

Quite early on, during a slew to Kochab, my PC lost contact with the mount, so I repeated the entire procedure. A move to Alkaid was successful (this was one of CPWI’s suggested sync stars), but again the wifi connection to the mount was lost. Very frustrating! Removing the “observatory” wifi connection from my PC didn’t solve the problem.

I returned the mount to Home (always a bit up and left of Polaris, reached repeatedly that evening), and this time I simply tried to slew to the Moon by hand using the CPWI slew control. Alas the gremlins continued to appear, and one of the compass directions in the CPWI slew control seemed to have a problem. The slew control would simply not advance in that direction! This was starting to sound like Apollo 13. Finally I asked David to just release the clutches and point the OTA at the Moon by hand. (The laser pointer at least was working.) Once at the Moon, with the tracking speed set to Lunar, all was strangely ok, all compass directions worked in the CPWI slew control, but one direction was much slower than the others. [Later I saw that CPWI listed a Dec of 89.6 deg in my images, so the problem was an incorrect and almost singular assumed location in polar coordinates. Bizarre.]

Anyway, I was now able to take many LX200 pictures of the Moon with my ASI294MCP camera attached, with a reasonably good focus, but with a strange slightly purple cast, not the deep red most lunar eclipse astrophotographers seem to encounter. Some examples are shown in the Astrophotography section, after post-processing to dilute the purple cast. Meanwhile Art had been using his Seestar 50 to capture lunar eclipse images, and these are much more satisfying; see cover, as well as the Astrophotography section.

Meade LX200 Adventures and the Lunar Eclipse. (cont.)

After we passed the end of the Umbral (total) stage of the eclipse, at 3:31 am Eastern, things grew rather more relaxed. My collection of Moon Music was aired in part. I recalled a small illuminated lunar globe that I had brought but had forgotten to set up, and took a few images of that for fun, one of which appears on p.3. Another is shown below.

The glow-dome, Meade LX200, and my setup for controlling the Meade and Celestron mount with CPWI and SharpCap; image capture at 4:05 am Eastern, 14 Mar 2025. The Moonglobe could obviously be used for some amusing photographic effects. Maybe next year. I left TAO about 4:38 am, and finally reached home about 5:40 am.

Astrophotography

Total Lunar Eclipse Images from 14 Mar 2025.

(TAO and elsewhere).

The high point for astroimaging in Mar 2025 was the total lunar eclipse of Fri 14 Mar 2025 (incidentally also “ π day”). In our case we gathered three ORION astronomers at the last moment for a Moongaze at TAO, starting at 11 pm and ending around 4:30 am, and made an effort to capture images of the Total Lunar Eclipse early in the morning of 14 Mar, using the Meade LX200 and Art’s Seestar 50. Organizational aspects of this trip appear in the preceding article. Some of those lunar images appear here, as well as a few contributed by ORION members from outside TAO.

(L to R) Ted Barnes, Art Allison and David Fields in the TAO building, preparing for a night of total lunar eclipse.

Total Lunar Eclipse Images from 14 Mar 2025.

(TAO and elsewhere).

Art Allison

Art captured a series of similar lunar exposures using his Seestar 50; these proved to be the most photogenic of the total lunar eclipse images captured at TAO that night. One appears on the cover this month, and is timestamped 2:57 am Eastern 14 Mar 2025. This image is stamped 3:02 am, and was subject to modest post-processing for brightness and contrast. This crop is *ca.* 779 px sq. (h and v differ by 2 px.)

Total Lunar Eclipse Images from 14 Mar 2025.

(TAO and elsewhere).

John Barnes

See discussion, page following.

Total Lunar Eclipse Images from 14 Mar 2025.

(TAO and elsewhere).

John Barnes

The image on the previous page was contributed by John Barnes, our ORION member from Louisville, Ky, and a cousin of the Editor.

Like Art, John owns a Seestar 50, which he used during the recent total lunar eclipse. John reports that this image was captured on 14 Mar 2025 at 2:53:19 am Eastern (in Louisville), and represents an approximately 5 minute stack. His coordinates were 38°18' 55" N, 85° 31' 28" W. He reports that the skies there were fairly clear, Bortle 6-7, which "is normal for good seeing in Louisville, Kentucky."

The Editor also post-processed this image, for brightness, sharpness and contrast, and cropped it slightly from the original 960x1044 px to 908 px sq.

The similarity between Art's and John's images is not accidental. Post-processing was used by the Editor to give them similar levels of brightness and contrast, and they were rotated and translated into coincidence, to the level of precision allowed by my image editing program.

It would be interesting to determine how much the location of the visible edge of the lunar disk changes in going from John's coordinates above to those of TAO, which are 35°49' 57" N, 84° 37' 04" W. Can one expect to observe a difference in the features recorded near the horizon in John's and Art's images, given their separation on the Earth (*ca.* 287 km)?

Or as a similar but simpler question, by about how much would a feature near the center of the lunar disk appear to be translated in comparing the two images, if they were taken at the same time?

Total Lunar Eclipse Images from 14 Mar 2025.

(TAO and elsewhere).

Ted Barnes

Ted used the Meade LX200 with a ZWO ASI294MCP camera attached, the mount operated by CPWI, and using SharpCap Pro to display and capture images. This is a cellphone image of the SCPro display, taken at 1:26 am, during the Penumbral stage of the eclipse. This is a live display of full-field (4144x2822 px), 0.25 ms images, with a camera gain of 400. The two large mare in the upper part of the image are (L to R) Mare Serenitatis and Mare Tranquillitatis. This image was post-processed for sharpness and contrast. A suggestion of a faint reddish tint in the lunar image is evident here.

Total Lunar Eclipse Images from 14 Mar 2025.

(TAO and elsewhere).

Ted's raw images during the Umbral phase somehow acquired a purple tint, which was largely suppressed in post-processing. Two examples of these images are shown here and on the following page. These Umbral phase images required a much longer exposure; this one was 1/15 sec at a gain of 514, taken at 2:41:44 am Eastern.

This shows the NE region of the Moon, with Mare Crisium near top right, and below it from L to R are the large Mare Serenitatis, Tranquillitatis, and Fecunditatis.

Total Lunar Eclipse Images from 14 Mar 2025.

(TAO and elsewhere).

In this image the large crater at lower left is Copernicus, adjacent to Mare Imbrium. This image was captured at 3:01:22 am Eastern, in the Umbral phase just after greatest eclipse. It used a 1/30 sec exposure with a gain of 570 (maximum) and was post-processed, primarily for increased contrast and to suppress a purple tint.

Total Lunar Eclipse Images from 14 Mar 2025.

(TAO and elsewhere).

Noah Frere

This dark nebula, a.k.a. The Boogeyman Nebula, or LDN 1622, resides in the constellation Orion, at a distance of about 500 ly. This curious object was the Sky Watcher target of the month for March, and was captured at TAO on March 3, 2025. I took this image with my Celestron 8" Edge HD, using a Hyperstar focal length reducer and a Bader CMOS Optimized UV/IR Cut Luminance Filter. This represents about 30 minutes of exposure; ideally it should have gone longer, to bring out more of the faint details.

LDN 1622, the Boogeyman Nebula in Orion.

Appendices

Astronomy

- tb

Some numbers are quoted to several-digit accuracy where appropriate.
Exact numerical relationships are indicated as such.

1 ly = 1 ly (Julian) = *exactly* 9 460 730 472 580. 8 km = 63 241. 077 084 ... AU
c = speed of light = *exactly* 299 792 458 m/s = *exactly* ☺ 1 ly/yr.
1 AU = *exactly* 149 597 870. 7 km
1 parsec (pc) = 3. 261 598 ... light years (ly)
1 yr (Julian) = *exactly* 365.25 d = *exactly* 31 557 600 s
1 d = *exactly* 86 400 s

distance to α Cen A = 1.346(2) pc = 4.390(8) ly
distance to the center of the galaxy ~ 8 kpc ~ 25 kly (considerable uncertainty)

1 nm = 1 nanometer = 10^{-9} m *exactly*
 H_{α} wavelength = 656.2 nm

+ 0.5 change in magnitude	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{1/5}$ x fainter =	1. 584 893 ... x fainter
+ 1 change in magnitude	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{2/5}$ x fainter =	2. 511 886 ... x fainter
+ 2 change in magnitude	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{4/5}$ x fainter =	6. 309 ... x fainter
+ 2.5 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^1 x fainter =	10 x fainter
+ 3 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{6/5}$ x fainter =	15. 848 ... x fainter
+ 4 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{8/5}$ x fainter =	39. 810 ... x fainter
+ 5 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^2 x fainter =	100 x fainter
+ 6 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{12/5}$ x fainter =	251. 188 ... x fainter
+ 7.5 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^3 x fainter =	1000 x fainter
+ 8 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{16/5}$ x fainter =	1584. 893 ... x fainter
+ 10 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^4 x fainter =	10 000 x fainter
+ 20 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^8 x fainter =	100 000 000 x fainter

Brightness is proportional to $1 / \text{distance}^2$

10 x more distant = *exactly* 10^2 x fainter = + 5 change in magnitude
 10^2 x more distant = *exactly* 10^4 x fainter = + 10 change in mag
 10^3 x more distant = *exactly* 10^6 x fainter = + 15 change in mag

Absolute magnitude M_{abs} is the brightness as seen from a distance of 10 pc
 M_{abs} (our sun) = 4.83

17th mag is about 1 optical photon / cm^2 s (Barnes's rule ☺)

Astronomy (cont.)

Some numbers are quoted to several-digit accuracy where appropriate. *Exact* numerical relationships are indicated as such.

R.A. = RA = Right Ascension = the angle ϕ around the celestial polar axis, usually quoted in hours, minutes, and seconds (*h m s*); analogous to longitude.

Dec = Declination = the angle θ above the celestial equator, usually quoted in degrees, minutes, and seconds ($^{\circ} \ ' \ ''$); analogous to latitude.

The RA (ϕ) and Dec (θ) angles, together with a reference epoch such as J2000.0, specify an object's direction in the sky.

A unit length vector ("unit vector") $\boldsymbol{\eta}$ pointing towards an object in the sky ("on the celestial sphere") in terms of RA (ϕ) and Dec (θ) angles is given by

$$\boldsymbol{\eta} = \cos(\theta) \cos(\phi) \mathbf{x} + \cos(\theta) \sin(\phi) \mathbf{y} + \sin(\theta) \mathbf{z} = C(c \mathbf{x} + s \mathbf{y}) + S \mathbf{z}$$

The arc angle Θ_{12} between any two directions in the sky $\boldsymbol{\eta}_1$ and $\boldsymbol{\eta}_2$ (or any two stars) using the dot product formula and some obvious abbreviations, satisfies

$$\cos(\Theta_{12}) = \sin(\theta_1)\sin(\theta_2) + \cos(\theta_1)\cos(\theta_2)\cos(\phi_1 - \phi_2) = S_1 S_2 + C_1 C_2 c_{1-2}$$

$$1 \text{ degree} = \pi/180 \text{ radians} = 1.745 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ arcmin} = \pi/10800 \text{ radians} = 2.909 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ arcsec} = 1 \text{ asec} = \pi/648000 \text{ radians} = 4.848 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ mas} = 10^{-3} \text{ asec} = 4.848 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ asec @ 1 km} = 4.848 \text{ mm}$$

$$1 \text{ asec @ 1 AU} = 725.3 \text{ km}$$

$$1 \text{ asec @ 1 pc} = 1.0000 \text{ AU}$$

$$1 \text{ mas @ 1 kpc} = 1.0000 \text{ AU}$$

JD = Julian Date (Astronomer's calendar) = a simple count of days starting at noon UT on Monday 1 Jan 4713 BC. That date and time was the start of Julian Day 0. The current JD can be inferred from the value on the cover of the Trapezium.

The 80 Brightest Stars

The 80 brightest stars (c/o Wikipedia), and their distances from Earth in light years, some with errors (from Gaia data).

1	Sirius	8.709	0.005	41	Menkalinan	81.1
2	Canopus	309.	16.	42	Atria	390.6
3	alpha Centauri A	4.395	0.008	43	Alhena	109.3
4	Arcturus	36.7	0.2	44	Peacock	178.8
5	Vega	25.04	0.07	45	Alsephina	80.6
6	Capella	42.81	0.26	46	Mirzam	492.7
7	Rigel	863.	78.	47	Polaris	432.6
8	Procyon	11.46	0.05	48	Alphard	177.3
9	Archenar	139.4	3.4	49	Hamal	65.8
10	Betelgeuse	498.	63.	50	Diphda	96.3
11	beta Centauri	392.	24.	51	Mizar	97.8
12	Altair	16.73	0.05	52	Nunki	227.8
13	alpha Crucis	322.	16.	53	Menkent	58.8
14	Aldebaran	66.64	1.05	54	Alpheratz	97.0
15	Antares	554.	94.	55	Mirach	197.4
16	Spica	250.	13.	56	Rasalhague	48.6
17	Pollux	33.78	0.09	57	Algieba	130.1
18	Fomalhaut	25.13	0.09	58	Kochab	130.9
19	Deneb	1410	200	59	Saiph	647.1
20	Mimosa	279.	23.	60	Denebola	35.9
21	Regulus	79.30	0.67	61	Algol	94.0
22	Adhara	405.	7.0	62	Tiaki	177.0
23	Castor	50.68	0.032	63	Muhlifain	130.2
24	Shaula	571.2	7.5	64	Aspidiske	765.6
25	Gacrux	88.56	0.43	65	Suhail	544.5
26	Bellatrix	252.4	10.2	66	Alphecca	75.0
27	Elnath	133.9	1.9	67	Mintaka	692.5
28	Miaplacidus	113.2	0.43	68	Sadr	1832.3
29	Alnilam	1980	540	69	Eltanin	154.3
30	Regor	1120	110	70	Schedar	228.2
31	Alnair	101.0	0.66	71	Naos	1083.6
32	Alnitak	736.	106.	72	Almach	393.0
33	Alioth	82.55	0.42	73	Caph	54.7
34	Dubhe	122.9	2.2	74	Izar	235.8
35	Mirfak	506.	13.	75	alpha Lupi	464.6
36	Wezen	1610	300	76	epsilon Centauri	427.5
37	Sargas	300.	41.	77	Dschubba	491.2
38	Kaus Australis	143.3	1.5	78	Larawag	63.7
39	Avior	605.	47.	79	eta Centauri	305.7
40	Alkaid	103.9	0.79	80	Merak	79.7

Notable Star-Pair Angles

Notable star pairs (from the set of the 80 brightest stars listed above) that are close to a multiple of 5° separation. The angles are in degrees.

		<u>Θ</u>	<u>Δθ</u>	<u>defect (%)</u>
Schedar	Caph	5	-0.085	1.7
Betelgeuse	Alnitak	10	0.017	0.17
Capella	Castor	30	-0.023	0.077
Procyon	Mirzam	30	-0.094	0.31
Elnath	Alnilam	30	-0.096	0.32
Alpheratz	Caph	30	0.060	0.20
Aldebaran	Pollux	45	0.013	0.029
Betelgeuse	Algol	50	-0.033	0.066
Alnitak	Naos	50	-0.049	0.098
Pollux	Alioth	60	0.065	0.11
Gacrux	Alphard	60	-0.001	0.002
Regulus	Bellatrix	70	-0.030	0.043
Sirius	Mirfak	80	-0.094	0.12
alpha_Centauri	Regulus	90	0.057	0.063
Vega	Denebola	90	-0.065	0.072
Fomalhaut	Caph	90	0.006	0.007
Deneb	Alnilam	120	0.059	0.049
Menkent	Mintaka	120	0.000	0.000
Sirius	Alphecca	135	-0.089	0.066
Aldebaran	Antares	170	-0.021	0.012

Exeunt

Stars

Alone in the night
On a dark hill
With pines around me
Spicy and still,

And a head full of stars
Over my head
White and topaz
And misty red;

Myriads were beating
Hearts of fire
The aeons
Cannot vex or tire;

Up the dome of heaven
Like a great hill
I watch them marching
Stately and still.

And I know that I
Am honored to be
Witness
Of so much majesty.

- Sara Teasdale (1884-1933)
fm. Flame and Shadow
(publ. 1920)

ORION and TAO (and Obed) General Information (links)

May be found at the following URLs:

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tamke-Allan_Observatory

<http://www.orioninc.org/>

<https://orionastronomy.wordpress.com>

<https://www.facebook.com/ORIONAstronomyTN/>

<https://www.facebook.com/groups/454645124557215>

<https://www.facebook.com/pages/Tamke-Allan%20Observatory/120477734665841>

<https://www.roanestate.edu/?349-Tamke-Allan-Observatory>

<https://www.roanestate.edu/pages/obs/index.htm>

<https://twitter.com/TAOremote>

ORIONastronomy@groups.io

Where is TAO?

334 Caney Creek Rd, Rockwood, TN 37854

N 35° 49' 57", W 84° 37' 04"; Alt. 324 m

Where is Obed?

Lilly Bluff Overlook

N 36° 06' 09", W 84° 43' 17"; Alt. 402 m

Nemo Bridge (on the bridge, E bank of Emory River)

N 36° 04' 07", W 84° 39' 43"; Alt. 268 m

Trapezium back issues online:

Vol. 49, Issue 4; Fri 15 Apr 2023:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8219253
Vol. 49, Issue 5; Fri 12 May 2023:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8216818
Vol. 49, Issue 6; Fri 16 Jun 2023:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8030659
Vol. 49, Issue 7; Fri 14 Jul 2023:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8140396
Vol. 49, Issue 8; Fri 18 Aug 2023:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8251302
Vol. 49, Issue 9; Fri 15 Sep 2023:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8336647
Vol. 49, Issue 10; Fri 13 Oct 2023:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8433081
Vol. 49, Issue 11; Fri 17 Nov 2023:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10138151
Vol. 49, Issue 12; Fri 15 Dec 2023:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10382618
Vol. 50, Issue 01; Fri 12 Jan 2024:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10483283
Vol. 50, Issue 02; Fri 16 Feb 2024:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10672625
Vol. 50, Issue 03; Fri 15 Mar 2024:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10822600
Vol. 50, Issue 04; Fri 12 Apr 2024:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10967036
Vol. 50, Issue 05; Fri 10 May 2024:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11176951
Vol. 50, Issue 06; Fri 14 Jun 2024:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11646971
Vol. 50, Issue 07, Fri 12 Jul 2024:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12735071
Vol. 50, Issue 08, Fri 16 Aug 2024:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13333599
Vol. 50, Issue 09, Fri 13 Sep 2024:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13742825
Vol. 50, Issue 10, Fri 11 Oct 2024:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13921735
Vol. 50, Issue 11, Fri 15 Nov 2024:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14171218
Vol. 50, Issue 12, Fri 13 Dec 2024:	https://zenodo.org/records/14394899
Vol. 51, Issue 01, Fri 10 Jan 2025:	https://zenodo.org/records/14630165
Vol. 51, Issue 02, Fri 14 Feb 2025:	https://zenodo.org/records/14873015
Vol. 51, Issue 03, Fri 14 Mar 2025:	https://zenodo.org/records/15015954
Vol. 51, Issue 04, Fri 11 Apr 2025:	https://zenodo.org/records/15200349

A generic link that lists Trapezium pdf issues (and other ORION documents) starting with the most recent, which does not require a specific zenodo document number, follows:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/rigel/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

Fin du journal

Frannie Astrocatticus

Fin du journal

Lucia Felix Caelestis

Fin du journal

Sunny Astrodogicus